

Grant Agreement No. 101131826

CoARA Boost

First progress report of WGs, including (Co-) Chairs Forum

Deliverable 4.3

CoARA Boost:

D4.3 First progress report of WGs, inc. (Co-)Chairs Forum

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Document information

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Document History

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0.4	28-03-2025	YERUN, ESF, WP4 Partners, (Co-)Chairs	Deliverable submitted.

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Abbreviations
ACA	Academic Career Assessment
ALLEA	The European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
EMCR	Early-and-Mid-Career Researchers
ERIP	Ethics and research integrity Policy for Responsible Research Assessment in Data and AI
ESF	European Scientific Foundation
GA	General Assembly
MCAA	Marie Curie Alumni Association
OF	Operational Framework
OI	Open Infrastructures
OI4RRA	Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
OSP	Operational support perimeter
PU	Public
R	Document report
SAGA	Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance (WG)

SB	Steering Board
SE	Science Europe
SG	Subgroup
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TD	Transdisciplinary
TIER	Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research (WG)
TLC	Task Leaders Committee
WG	Working group
WP	Work package
YERUN	Young European Research Universities Network

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PART I: Contextual Information

1. Executive Summary

The overall objectives of WP4 (*Support to CoARA Working Groups*) are to provide operational support to WGs and to enable the sharing of experiences and linking up through the (Co-)Chairs Forums. Deliverable (D)4.1 *WGs' Operational Framework report* included the Operational Framework used to establish the operational support perimeter between WP4 partners and WGs (in addition to the communication tools and procedures, the endorsement framework, the monitoring report template, and other useful guidelines). D4.2 includes the revision of the Operational Framework report and the present document (*D4.3 First progress report of Working Groups (WGs), inc. (Co-)Chairs Forum*) aims to maintain a comprehensive overview of all WG contributions towards the reform of academic assessment. This report is led and managed by YERUN, within the Horizon Europe project CoARA Boost. A final progress report (D4.4) will be produced by MCAA by the end of the project (M36).

The core of the document presents the key activities and outputs by each WG, alongside the narrative assessment and lessons learnt extracted from their experience during implementation. This report focuses on the progress and outcomes achieved thus far achieved by the WGS. It demonstrates the value of their contributions to CoARA and the wider research assessment community. The report also includes the outcomes of the two (Co-)Chairs Forums alongside an overview of the commitments covered by the WGs during the first call until M18 of the project.

2. Project Summary

Over 800 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and principles for reforming the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations, outlined in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. They have also committed to implement changes within their organisations. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, CoARA, offers a platform for collaboration and mutual learning. However, given the complexity of the reform process, providing support for institutions to test, design, and carry out in-depth institutional changes is crucial to implement the Agreement commitments.

The CoARA Boost project, funded by the European Union, strengthens CoARA's operational capacity. It provides a means to develop a critical mass for reforming research assessment, to generate gravitas for new members as well as to investigate and implement new models for research assessment. CoARA Boost i) strengthens CoARA's operational capacity, ii) catalyses knowledge development, policy evolution, and institutional change in research assessment, iii) facilitates the collection and exchange of information, and iv) widens the coalition's membership in Europe and beyond. The project is crucial for the global growth of the reform-focused community, amplifying collaboration and enhancing knowledge exchange and mutual learning within the coalition.

Main actions carried out by the CoARA Boost project include:

- Expanding the operational support to the coalition, including enabling multiple approaches of knowledge sharing among the coalition members.
- Supporting signatories in compiling and executing on their action plans towards the achievement of the agreed 10 commitments. As well as based on the action plans establishing an observatory of responsible research assessment practices reaching well beyond the realm of European stakeholders.
- Providing operational assistance to Working Groups in their exploration of new models of research assessment.
- Catalysing change via the CoARA Boost cascade funding program that will be facilitating institutional reform pathways to a significant number of organisations of different types and across geographical areas as well as solutions and resources that members of the coalition can rely on in their efforts in implementing core commitments of CoARA.
- Expanding the outreach of European efforts to reform research assessment by growing the membership of CoARA globally and fostering international cooperation on evolutions in research assessment.

3. Summary of the Deliverable

D4.3 is a progress report. The deliverable draws upon the individual monitoring reports that each of the 13 WG's (Co-)Chairs completed in November 2024 and which were subsequently updated in February 2024.

Its primary objectives are (1) to compile all the contributions made by the most central part of CoARA, the WGs, in one document and (2) to include the processes and key outcomes resulting from the (Co-)Chairs Forums conducted up to this point.

Work Package 4 is a key WP within CoARA Boost, dedicating its resources to supporting the functioning of the WGs. As such, it supports the operational capacity of WGs where needed and ensures knowledge sharing and linking up through the (Co-)Chairs Forums. Additionally, WP4 serves as an essential liaison between the WGs and the CoARA Secretariat.

As mentioned, the report compiles the outcomes of the self-assessment process conducted by the (Co-)Chairs in agreement with their respective WG members. By consolidating all WG contributions to date into a single document, it directly supports CoARA's connectivity and coordination efforts. Additionally, the report integrates the results of the (Co-)Chairs Forums, summarising key conclusions and outcomes in the final section.

PART 2: Working Groups Progress Report and (Co-) Chairs Forums

1. Introduction

Part 2 contains the core of this report. It presents the outputs, narrative progress, and lessons learned from the first 13 CoARA working groups (WGs) over 18 months of implementation. Rather than revisiting initial work plans, this progress report compiles the activities and outcomes of the WGs, including their contributions to the reform of research assessment in absolute terms. **All contributions from the WGs are inherently valuable. The aim of this report is not to audit or scrutinise their adherence to initial projections but to highlight their achieved progress and tangible outcomes.**

Deliverable (D)4.1 *WGs' Operational Framework report* included the Operational Framework used to establish the operational support perimeter between WP4 partners and WGs (in addition to the communication tools and procedures, the endorsement framework, the monitoring report template, and other useful guidelines). D4.2 (*Revised Operational Framework report*) includes the revision of the Operational Framework, submitted at the same time as this document. The present document (D4.3 *First progress report of Working Groups (WGs), inc. (Co-)Chairs Forum*) aims to maintain a comprehensive overview of all WG contributions towards the reform of academic assessment. A final progress report (D4.4) will be produced by the end of the project (M36).

The report is structured as follows: section 2 presents the methods applied for compiling WG contributions; section 3 provides an overview of the commitments that WGs have been addressing; section 4 offers a detailed account of each WG's progress, activities, outputs, narrative assessments and lessons learned; section 5 describes the processes and outcomes of the Co-Chairs Forums; and section 6 concludes the report by highlighting the next steps and remaining tasks for the WP.

2. Methodology

The CoARA Working Groups have been actively implementing their plans since November 2023, when the first 10 WGs commenced their work, with the remaining 3 WGs beginning at a later stage. Figure 1 illustrates the specific starting months for each WG.

WP4 elaborated a monitoring framework consisting of a monitoring plan and template. The purpose of the CoARA WG monitoring or progress report is to facilitate:

- Reflexive self-governance of CoARA WGs,
- Monitoring and reporting of progress to the CoARA Secretariat and Steering Board,
- Collection of lessons learned to improve performance and processes,
- Coordination among WGs to boost the collective impact of CoARA.

Regarding the monitoring process, the [CoARA Rules of Procedure](#) indicate that the submission of the monitoring template (progress report) will take place once a year: 'Every year, an established WG will submit a progress report to the Secretariat, which will review it'. The monitoring plan is structured around the following submission deadlines.

- 1st report: 31 October 2024 (submitted).
- 2nd report: 31 October 2025.
- 3rd report: 31 October 2026.

The first progress report submission was postponed to 31st of November in order to grant (Co-)Chairs more time to comment on the monitoring report template and accommodate changes following the second (Co-)Chair meeting in Helsinki – see section 5 for greater details.

The revised monitoring template can be found in D4.2, *the Revised Operational Framework report*. This template aims to establish a unified structure and standardised format for reporting progress. Each WG conducts a self-assessment and documents their conclusions in the individual progress reports. At the end of November 2024, WP4 partners retrieved these reports from the CoARA SharePoint, where each WG can see each other's progress and key activities.

To ensure the reports reflect the latest activities, WP4 partners asked WG (Co-)Chairs to review and update their submissions (covering also the months December 2024 to 27 February 2025).

Following these updates, WP4 leads consolidated the reports into a single document and requested WP4 partners to confirm the accuracy of the content with

each WG's (Co-)Chairs. In recognition of their contributions to this deliverable, all participating (Co-)Chairs will be acknowledged as authors.

3. CoARA Commitments

This section provides an overview (and updates the list included at proposal stage by WGs) of the CoARA Commitments currently being addressed by the WGs, highlighting those receiving greater or lesser attention. Its aim is to identify areas requiring increased focus in future calls for CoARA WGs.

Figure 1 illustrates the alignment between WG and specific CoARA Commitments. It also shows the starting month for each WG. The complete list of CoARA Commitments is available on the [CoARA website](#).

WG	Start Date	Commitment
1. Early and Mid-Career Researchers	November 2023	1, 2, 6, 7, 8 & 10
2. Ethics and Research Integrity Policy for Responsible Research Assessment in Data and AI (ERIP)	March 2024	1-10
3. Evaluating Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research globally	June 2024	1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8 & 10
4. Experiments in Assessments	October 2023	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 & 10
5. Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals	November 2023	1, 2, 3, 4, 7 & 8
6. Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment	November 2023	1, 2, 3 & 4
7. Recognising and rewarding Peer Review	November 2023	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8
8. Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)	October 2023	1 & 2
9. Responsible metrics and indicators	November 2023	2, 3, 6, 8 & 10
10. Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance (SAGA)	November 2023	1, 2, 3, 5, 7 & 8
11. Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research (TIER)		1, 5, 8 & 9

12. Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment (OI4RRA)	February 2024	1, 2, 5, 6, 7 & 10
13. Towards Transformations:	January 2024	
a. Transdisciplinary Research SG		a. 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8
b. Applied/Practice-Based Research SG		b. 1, 2
c. Societal Impacts SG		c. 1, 2

Fig. 1 Commitments covered by the CoARA WGs

From Fig. 1 the following can be concluded:

- **Commitment 1 & 2** are frequently mentioned across nearly all groups.
- **Commitment 3**: is frequently mentioned, but slightly less than 1 and 2.
- **Commitment 4** is mentioned less frequently; not covered by several WGs.
- **Commitment 5**: is mentioned infrequently; omitted by many groups.
- **Commitment 6, 7, 8 & 10** are moderately mentioned.
- **Commitment 9** is rarely mentioned; significantly underrepresented across groups.

In general, the **least mentioned** commitment is **Commitment 9**, followed by **Commitment 5 and Commitment 4**. These insights shape the upcoming and last call for Working Groups within the CoARA Boost project.

4. Working Groups Progress:

The following section outlines the progress made by the WGs in terms of outputs, narrative assessment and lessons learnt, since the beginning of their implementation (see *Fig. 1* for an overview of the starting months per WG).

The **Outputs/deliverables/activities** section of each WG outlines reports, surveys, workshops, case studies etc. that showcase the activities carried out or that will be carried out during the implementation period of each WG. These are organised into “Completed”, “Ongoing”, “Minor issues”, “Major issues” and “Future” outputs/deliverables/activities. Note that not all sections will appear for each WG, but only those that are relevant within the context of the WG.

The **narrative assessment** of progress will detail current progress, including successes and hurdles encountered during implementation of the workplan.

The **lessons learnt** section within each WG will record operational, managerial, content-based and other lessons and learnings resulting from a reflection on the hitherto implementation of the **workstream**.

The following sub-sections include the progress of the 13 WGs in alphabetical order.

1. WG: Early and Mid-Career Researchers

The mission of the WG Early-and-Mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture is to collect best practices, monitor impacts, and develop guidelines, models, and a toolbox for implementation for EMCR assessment and methodologies to foster a more inclusive research culture.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Emma Day (CRAC/Vitae), Sebastian Dahle (Eurodoc), Pil Saugmann (Eurodoc).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Minor issues with outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Landscaping report of Academic Positions in European National systems:** Initial mapping has been drafted (March 2025) drawing on expertise from EURODOC and the WG. There will be a consultation phase drawing on WG members and EURODOC through a series of workshops focussing on various country groupings. This will lead to a final report in the summer of 2025.
- **Landscaping Report of Habilitation Practices:** An initial mapping has been drafted (March 2025) drawing on the expertise of EURODOC and the WG. There will be a consultation phase drawing on WG members and EURODOC through a series of workshops focussing on various country groupings. This will lead to a final report in the Summer.

Narrative assessment:

The WG has faced significant delays due to an overly ambitious scope and limited resources, despite strong interest and a membership of 80 people. EURODOC has made significant progress in completing the landscaping phase for 15 European countries for both reports. There has been a great deal of work to do this and it has provided a strong basis for the working group to move forward. They will now enter a consultation phase based on the existing documents and drawing on different country expertise.

The group will scale back their original proposal and for now focus on completing these two reports to a high standard and then consider dissemination.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Realistic initial proposal	The EMCR WG proposal was extremely ambitious and to deliver completely would require additional funding and dedicated resources. The Group had to adapt what they are able to achieve in the time available and focus on where they can be of most benefit to COARA.
Time and resource	The work has been delayed, and this has largely been due to other funded priorities. This will always be a challenge with voluntary working groups.
Size of working group	With over 80 members it is hard to manage the working group and that has also slowed progress. Members need to be given clear tasks: e.g. Review this document for your own country in order to engage properly.
Cross working with other groups	Given the topic of this working group, it would be useful to review the outputs of other working groups from the perspective of this particular cohort.

Fig. 2 WG 1 Learning and adaptive management Table

2. Ethics and Research Integrity Policy for Responsible Research Assessment in Data and Artificial Intelligence (ERIP)

The CoARA Working Group on Ethics and Research Integrity for Responsible Research Assessment in Data and Artificial Intelligence (ERIP) aims to shape policies, methods, and tools for responsible research assessment in the digital age. The WG works to embed research ethics and integrity into how digital objects, including data and AI, are evaluated across disciplines. ERIP works to realise the Principles and Commitments of CoARA within the digital space of current scientific and higher education research outputs. The WG focuses on setting standards for the ethical collection, analysis, and interpretation of data, as well as the responsible deployment of AI in research evaluation.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are Francis P. Crawley (GCPA & CODATA) (Coordinator), Pil Maria Saugmann (EURODOC), Kris Dierickx (KU Leuven), Perihan Elif Ekmekçi (TOBB ETÜ), Cyrus Walther (CODATA/ISC), Chiedozie Ike (Ambrose Alli University), Mara de Souza Freitas (Universidade Católica Portuguesa), Gitanjali Yadav (IISER Bhopal)

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Survey of National Chapters and other WGs** (October 2024): CoARA-ERIP circulated a survey to the NCs and WGs to ascertain their concerns regarding the assessment of digital objects and to identify avenues for collaboration/convergence.
- **Workshops, webinars, meeting contributions, and outreach events** (ongoing until December 2025): CoARA-ERIP regularly hosts and participates in webinars and meetings to discuss current issues related to the ethical use of data/AI in research and the challenges/opportunities presented by digital objects for research assessment. The working group is collaborating with several partners in this endeavour, including academies of sciences in India, China, EU, Mongolia, Belarus, and across Africa as well as with CODATA IDPC, EOSC-Future/RDA AI & Data Visitation WG, the Technical University of Munich (TUM) – Exeter University's Ethical Data Initiative (EDI), and OSSci and their partners of the above. For a list of upcoming and past ERIP engagements, see [here](#).

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Policy framework for ethical research assessment in the digital age** (March 2026): The working group is developing a policy document to guide the ethical

assessment of digital objects alongside the responsible use of data and AI in research assessment procedures. Currently, CoARA-ERIP is working via its workstreams 1, 2, and 3, and in collaboration with the Open Source Science Initiative (OSSci) and their Map of Open Source Science (MOSS), to draft a **Landscaping Instrument** (December 2025), which maps the policies and tools related to the safeguarding of research ethics and integrity related to the use of data and AI in research. This mapping will enable ERIP to synthesise best practices and address the gaps in existing mechanisms for the policy framework. Concomitantly, the WG is also developing a **Framing Document** (June 2025) to structure the drafting of the policy guidance documents and support the digital framework's architecture it is developing.

- **Checklist for self-evaluation in research assessment** (June 2025): The working group, via workstream 2, is developing a checklist designed to guide researchers and research departments/institutions in the evaluation of digital objects as outputs of their research. It covers key aspects of responsible research assessment, including research ethics, research integrity, data integrity, AI integration, and stakeholder engagement.
- **The ERIP Handbook on integrity, data, and AI in research evaluation** (March 2026): The ERIP Handbook on integrity, data, and AI in research evaluation will offer a comprehensive guide to navigating ethical complexities and leveraging digital advancements in contemporary research assessment practices. The handbook will be supplemented with a) a selected list of references for ethical research evaluation of data and AI, b) a mapping of engaged parties and projects, and c) a glossary of key terminology. Currently, workstream 1 is developing the **glossary** of key terms (December 2025).
- **Digital toolkit for the responsible assessment of digital objects** (March 2026): CoARA-ERIP, via its workstream 3, in collaboration with OSSci and other partners, is developing a toolkit, comprising practical resources such as templates and technology-enabled tools, that would facilitate the assessment of digital contributions to research, as well as the responsible use of data and AI in research assessment. Currently, the working group is collecting **user stories** (May 2025) from research-funding and research-performing organisations to assess the needs of the research community for the development of the toolkit. Together with workstream 2, workstream 3 is compiling a comprehensive **list of metrics and indicators** (June 2025) currently used to evaluate research in the digital environment.

Narrative assessment:

CoARA-ERIP had its kick-off hybrid meeting at the Royal Academies for Science and the Arts of Belgium in Brussels on 20 March 2024 with representatives of the European Commission, where it presented its [Organisation and Workplan](#). The

meeting led to the development of the following key objectives to guide CoARA-ERIP's efforts:

- O1: The creation of an outreach program to shape policy, institutional, and societal change, promoting a culture of responsible data and AI research.
- O2: Developing policies, methods, and tools to enable the responsible evaluation of digital contributions to science and research assessments, promoting research ethics and integrity in scientific practices.
- O3: The piloting of a comprehensive toolkit for the implementation of best practices in research assessment for data and AI.

CoARA-ERIP works through three workstreams, which structure the research, writing, and technical development efforts needed to attain the three objectives outlined above. The working group's operations are decentralised with core groups of WG members taking the lead on coordinating the different outputs within each workstream. This strategy allows the work of ERIP to proceed without bottlenecks. Coordination/collaboration between the 3 workstreams is achieved via monthly WG meetings. CoARA-ERIP has also been collaborating with partners within and beyond the coalition through a series of outreach events to systematically gather best practices, as well as exchange ideas, on the ethical assessment of digital objects. ERIP's work has been enriched through the active participation of a globally representative and trans-disciplinary membership.

Conceptual challenges persist given the ambitious scope of the working group's workplan, particularly in developing standardised qualitative and quantitative assessment indicators for digital research contributions. The complexity of integrating AI into research evaluation and ensuring diverse stakeholder engagement across disciplines and geographies remains a key focus. Additionally, managing a multidisciplinary, voluntary expert community requires an enormous investment of time and resources. Collaboration with other national chapters and working groups is steadily developing and will be more heavily engaged as CoARA-ERIP matures in its outputs and the work of other CoARA WGs and NCs develops.

The working group is advancing steadily with its workplan, learning from the engagements and refining its methodologies while also growing its international collaboration. It is forging a path toward policies and systems architecture aimed at contributing to a more inclusive, ethical, and transparent research evaluation system that values the generation and contribution of knowledge at all levels. Through its extensive engagement and structured workstreams, ERIP works by example as well as through outputs, setting a precedent for a global and inclusive approach to responsible research assessment practices in the EU and worldwide.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Steep learning curve and information gaps	Developing standardised and widely applicable qualitative and quantitative indicators and metrics for digital objects has proven to be even more complex than anticipated. Different disciplines, institutional policies, and technological advancements demand adoptable and adaptable digital research assessment frameworks that accommodate diverse research, institutional, and geographical needs.
Ground-up, decentralised operations	It was important for the WG to engage a diverse community of stakeholders across geographies, disciplines, and career stages to incorporate different needs, resource contexts, and cultures in the development of inclusive outputs. However, ensuring that insights from external partners translate into actionable outcomes within ERIP's frameworks requires improved collaboration tracking and integration strategies. The co-chair model adopted by ERIP has been effective in providing leadership. As the work progresses, this decentralised bottom-up approach is proving beneficial in ensuring the most comprehensive and inclusive working methodology.
Coordination	ERIP's global and trans/interdisciplinary nature has required adaptive coordination mechanisms. Balancing input from experts across multiple fields, institutions, and geographical locations has highlighted the need for streamlined communication channels and well-defined workflows. Virtual engagement strategies, including webinars and structured meetings, have proven effective but require continued optimisation to ensure full participation.
Specialised expertise	Since one of CoARA-ERIP's key objectives is to develop deployable technology-enabled tools to facilitate the responsible assessment of data and AI, there was an early challenge of a skills-gap. However, by collaborating with partners, such as OSSci, who were aligned on the working group's goals, such skills and expertise gaps were bridged to make progress on the toolkit. CoARA-ERIP has appreciated the flexibility of including non-CoARA signatories in its discussions. Without these voices,

	<p>particularly from the Global South, the working group would not be able to achieve the comprehensive and inclusive research assessment guidance for digital objects it seeks. By including this broader expertise, CoARA-ERIP has also provided a channel for CoARA to become better known outside the European context, as well as bring in new CoARA signatories. CoARA-ERIP is particularly grateful to the CoARA Steering Committee for its flexibility in this regard.</p>
<p>Time and resource management</p>	<p>The (Co-)Chairs and membership have proven enormously committed and willing to juggle CoARA-ERIP responsibilities with their own primary institutional commitments. The Organisation and Workplan was developed to meet the needs of a working group driven entirely by volunteers with a limited budget. The work has been supported by the expertise and enthusiasm of highly committed participants who value the potential contribution of this team approach to research evaluation in the digital space.</p>

Fig. 3 WG 2 Learning and adaptive management Table

3. Evaluating Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research globally

The mission of the WG Evaluating Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Research Globally is to identify distinct and shared methods and principles used in SSH assessment through a mapping of approaches across disciplines, countries, and language communities and foster community consensus around principles to underpin the framework for research assessment.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: *Gabi Lombardo*, European Alliance of SSH (EASSH), *Janne Pölönen* (Federation of Finnish Learned Societies) and *Michael Ochsner* (University of Lausanne).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Bringing together different SSH communities and experts** (June 2024 – June 2026). Disciplines in SSH are very different and the WG will encourage collaboration between different experts. All experts will work in task forces together, take advantage of surveys and gathering practices.

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Development of adaptable frameworks** (June 2024 – June 2025): The WG will begin working on a simple ‘theory of evaluation’ to inform evaluation of SSH scholarship at both institutional and individual academic levels. Data gathering, best practices and innovation in evaluation are to be included.
- **Facilitate mutual learning beyond Europe** (June 2024–2026) collaborating with experts and international actors that will be involved in data gathering as full partners of the WG.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **National chapters analysis** (June 2025) of key practices and research evaluation procedures in different Member States.
- **Peer review report** (June 2025) on selection procedures, standards and disciplinary practices through a dedicated Task Group (linking with another WG on peer review).

Narrative assessment:

The WG on Evaluating SSH globally has been one of the last 3 WGs approved in late 2023.

Although it is too early to report on the working group actual achievements, the Co-chairs of this working group are revising the timetable in order to deliver outputs in line with the framework established by the CoARA steering group. Furthermore, the members of this working group are capitalising from the work already developed in other working groups in which they are involved or can access information.

On 29 November 2024, the original plan submitted for the WG was revised to be delivered by 5 task groups. In February 2025, the first 3 task groups reported on their developments. TG1 has already analysed the mention of SSH in over 100 CoARA plans and identified the context in which the mention is made. The TG 2 merged with TG3 around the principle and values of evaluation. A set of guidelines will be produced and discussed at third meeting in May to be then circulated in June for feedback and in December at the next CoARA general assembly (if possible).

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
CoARA	It was noted that many of the actors engaged in CoARA from the universities seem to have a relatively low impact due to their position in the management ranking. Although universities are committed to improving the research evaluation, the guidelines and the narrative of CoARA is either entrusted to individual researchers or to policy officers. It seems that the movement still lacks a full commitment from top management of the universities.
Research councils	Although there are some National chapters, and national evaluation agencies have signed up for CoARA, the impact on research councils is still limited.
SSH specifically	There is very little attention given to the fact that SSH has different processes and procedures compared to STEM. Many of the general guidelines to evaluate research often rest on outputs like patents or spin-offs of research which are not relevant for most of the SSH disciplines. Furthermore, too often there is no dedicated attention to how the career development, the evaluation of projects and the assessment of "other" outputs can be understood. The disciplines also are still very fragmented and diverse both in their practice and developments. For example, in the use of technology in research, there is still a big difference across researchers even within a single discipline.

Fig. 4 WG 3 Learning and adaptive management Table

4. WG: Experiments in Assessment: Idea Generation, Co-creation, and Piloting

The mission of WG Experiments in Assessment is to form an incubator for experimental ideas in research assessment. It aims to establish a process to enable change: collecting, refining, and proposing pilots to drive new initiatives. The group creates space for collaboration and brainstorming on unconventional ideas to shift assessment in line with the goals of CoARA.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Noémie Aubert Bonn (Hasselt University and Amsterdam UMC) Simone Sacchi (European University Institute), Sean Sapcaru (Luxembourgish National Research Fund, FNR).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Survey** gathering experimental ideas from the community. Executed between Q2 and Q4 2024. The survey gathered 90 responses, mostly from within Europe, but from a wide range of research-related roles.
- **Discussion workshops** (Two public, one internal) were conducted in Q3 2024 and brainstormed experimental ideas in the community.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Idea catalogue** for experiments in research assessment – Survey synthesis and construction of an online interactive catalogue of ideas. The concept and configuration of the catalogue was discussed at an in-person WG meeting in Lisbon (January 2025), and a prototype is being prepared for a soft launch to CoARA Working Groups, National Chapters, and the CoARA Steering Board in Q2 2025. A full launch of the catalogue is planned for Q4 2025.
- **White paper on WG process** detailing the tool development and process used in the working group will be published, adding value for those not directly involved in the project or for subsequent similar initiatives. The white paper is in preparation. Rather than releasing it as standalone document, it will now be integrated into the idea's catalogue platform. It will be included in the prototype from Q2 2025.
- **Literature review:** the literature review continues as a living and expanding activity, both as a complementary activity to the idea catalogue as well as to identify potential resources and literature that can serve as evidence/learnings for experiments in the catalogue. A living version of this review will be published by Q3 2025.

Minor issues with outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Pilot experiments and report:** the group has decided not to pursue the final deliverable/workstream of implementing and piloting experiments within the timeline of the WG due to the lack of time and resources. Instead, the group will focus on the idea catalogue, providing as much information as possible to allow any community members to run experiments. Beyond the lifetime of the WG, members will consider how to support organisations who want to pursue the experimental ideas in the catalogue.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Public open/online seminar:** *New planned output from the discussion within the WG:* A final public webinar/seminar is planned by the group upon the full launch of the idea catalogue to present the catalogue as well as the process followed by the group and opportunities for pilots based on the experimental ideas showcased. Q4 2025.

Narrative assessment:

Since the launch in November 2023, the WG on Experiments in Assessment has conducted a survey to collect ideas for experiments in assessment processes, practices, and policies. 90 responses were collected, encompassing a wide range of research-related roles. Three workshops were conducted (two public, one internal) to further discuss and elaborate experimental ideas. These workshops helped with an internal brainstorm to develop further ideas with the Working Group. An in-person meeting of the group was held in Lisbon in January 2025 and was used to align on a structure and concept for the idea catalogue. It was agreed that the catalogue will be an online and living resource that allows input from the research community. The concept for a white paper on the process of the Working Group will now also be integrated into the online idea catalogue platform. Soft launch webinars are planned for the CoARA community (CoARA National Chapters, Working Groups, and the Steering Board), and a public webinar will be organised on the full public launch of the catalogue before the end of 2025. In addition, the literature review which is also a living activity continues. A search strategy was developed by the group, and results (>2000 papers) are currently being screened for relevance. A living version of this literature review is planned to be released in Autumn 2025.

Finally, the WG has decided not to pursue the implementation and piloting of experiments within the scope of the Working Group timeline due to a lack of time and resources. Focus now shifts onto the idea catalogue to ensure that it provides the necessary information to allow any community members to run experiments.

Beyond the lifetime of the WG, members will consider how to support organisations who want to pursue the experimental ideas in the catalogue.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Resource load and volunteer work	Progress has been slower than anticipated due to competing priorities among WG members, as this work is not their primary responsibility. Patience and continued support for active contributors are essential to maintaining momentum.
Reaching the community	Expanding outreach beyond the immediate community through initiatives such as surveys and workshops remains challenging, even with the support of CoARA, other WGs, and national chapters. Limited awareness, low engagement with communications, and gaps in existing networks contribute to these difficulties.
Setting the values of the group first	Taking the time in establishing shared values and a common working approach fosters a positive, open, and inclusive culture. This alignment enhances collaboration and ensures collective progress toward common goals.

Fig. 5 WG 4 Learning and adaptive management Table

5. Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals

The overall mission of the Working Group is to improve practices in the assessment of research proposals, ultimately supporting higher quality and more impactful projects, in line with the principles and commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, while respecting the autonomy of each member.

The (Co-)Chairs of this WG are:

- European Commission (Georgios Papanagnou, Javier Lopez Albacete).
- German Research Foundation, Germany (Matthias Kiesselbach, Anna Christa).
- Knowledge Foundation, Sweden (Yvonne Fors).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Survey** (February–March 2024) about the understanding and operationalisation of research quality by research funders, and about their practices in selecting and guiding reviewers. This document was shared with the WG members, but also with additional research funding organisations.
- **Workshop** (June 2024) on how to best recognise and foster the diversity of research contributions (outputs, activities and practices), by using the funding prerequisites, the design of funding programmes and the review criteria. All WGs, plus additional representatives from other research funding organisation, were invited.
- **Workshop** (December 2024) on the selection of reviewers to align with the Agreement commitments. All WGs, plus additional representatives from other research funding organisation, were invited.
- **Workshop** (January 2025) on guidance to reviewers to foster responsible research assessment. All WGs, plus additional representatives from other research funding organisation, were invited.
- **Report** (November 2023 – April 2024) on research quality – understanding and operationalisation. All WG members have been consulted for contributions and comments.
- **Report** (June and October 2024) compiling the comments to the relevant deliverables of the CoARA WG “Recognizing and Rewarding Peer-Review”.

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Survey** (due February–March 2025) about what information is requested from applicants, by research funding organisations, and in what format. This document will be shared with the WG members, but also with additional research funding organisations.
- **Report** (due November 2023 – August 2025) on a bibliographic analysis, to gather existing practices, evidence and recommendations. Available to all Working Group members for contributions and comments.
- **Report** (due January 2024 – August 2025) on good/best practices and potential recommendations about selection criteria and evaluation processes. Draft elements of the report available to all WG members for contributions and comments.
- **Report** (due January 2024 – April 2025, there may be some delay) on challenges and good/best practices, toolboxes and potential recommendations, about the selection of reviewers, the composition of panels, the guidance to reviewers and the recognition of peer-review. Draft available to all WG members for contributions and comments.
- **Report** (due February 2025 – August 2025) on good/best practices, toolboxes and potential recommendations, about information requested from applicants. Draft will be available to all WG members for contributions and comments
- **Report** (August 2024 – August 2025) on innovative procedures. The draft will be available to all Working Group members for contributions and comments

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Workshop** (May 2025) on how information requested from applicants can enable qualitative assessment and recognition of diverse outputs, practices and activities. This document will be shared with the WG members, but also with additional research funding organisations.

Narrative assessment:

The WG began by surveying current practices and gathering ideas to improve how reviewers are selected and guided, and how selection criteria are defined – all in support of the Agreement commitments. This initial survey informed discussions on what constitutes research quality among funding organizations, culminating in a finalised report. The group continues these discussions through regular meetings and workshops, focusing on best practices for selection criteria, assessment strategies, and reviewer guidance, with a special emphasis on recognizing diverse research contributions. They are now drafting reports that outline good practices, challenges, and recommendations, and plan to launch a second survey to explore

how to best request applicant information—ensuring a balanced mix of qualitative and quantitative data without over-relying on traditional metrics like journal reputation or impact factors.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Time and resource of the group members	The (Co-)Chairs face difficulty in mobilising written contributions by the Working Group members. Consequently, the (Co-)Chairs organise workshops for focused discussions that allow gathering further information from the group members.
Time and resource of the (Co-)Chairs	The organisation of surveys, the organisation of workshops, and the drafting of reports, demand significant time from the (Co-)Chairs. This may have been underestimated and is partly linked to difficulties in mobilising written contributions of group members.
Surveys	Challenge of designing the surveys. The objectives and estimated outputs of the work need to be very precisely defined in order to design survey questions that allow the gathering of the appropriate information.
Existing practices vs. new practices	Significant and very useful knowledge can be gained from analysing existing practices. However, some forward looking discussions on new practices also need to be conducted. The balance between the two is not easy to define, and topic specific.
Synergies with other groups	The Group has only limited knowledge of the precise topics under investigation by other Working Groups, and their progress. An effective knowledge sharing platform would have been needed from the start of the operation of the Working Groups. Also, (Co-)Chairs have only limited time for interacting with other Working Groups, as the tasks of a given Working Group are already very demanding.

Fig. 6 WG 5 Learning and adaptive management Table

6. Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment

The mission of the WG Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment is to foster an academic culture that values diverse competencies, interactions, and communications in all languages without exclusions or priorities.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are:

- Janne Pölonen (The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies),
- Emanuel Kulczycki (Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań),
- Monica Dietl (Initiative for Science in Europe),
- Gian Maria Greco, (Marie Curie Alumni Association).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Policy advice** (10/2025) to (a) HEI and RPO and (b) RFO and Evaluation agencies: Policy advice on incentivizing multilingual academic culture building on Deliverable 1-3. Dissemination: Zenodo, webinar. 10/2025.
- **Workshops and webinars recordings** (ongoing) to disseminate the WG, mid-term and final results.

Minor issues with outputs/deliverables/activities

- **Landscape report** (04/2025, slightly delayed) on the current state and best practices of multilingualism: Landscape analysis: literature reviews, surveys (researchers & organisations), bibliometric analyses. Dissemination: Zenodo, Webinar.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **White Paper** (05/2025) Importance and issues of multilingualism in relation to assessment reform.
- **Toolbox** for language aware assessments (10/2025). Devising and testing tools, guidelines and models to help address language biases and supporting language skills. Zenodo, webinar.
- **Implementation proposal** (10/2025) for CoARA on language aware assessments. Actionable recommendations: outputs 1-5 & co-creation with WG and interested CoARA members. Zenodo, webinar, position paper.
- **Position paper** (10/2025) on multilingualism in research assessment (summary of results of the WG activities)

- **Translations** of outputs (10/2025).

Narrative assessment:

Since kick-off 3 November 2023, WG has finalised Action plan in February 2024, drafted Definitions & Glossary & Literature review on current state, conducted 3 researcher surveys (CNR, MCAA, ECSPM) and survey to organisations, and conducted bibliometric analyses of language coverage in databases. WG organised a public webinar 26 September 2024 15:00-16:30 CET. WG currently involves 76 experts from 43 organisations, with regular monthly meeting for WG members and coordination team.

The main challenge is the lack of time and resources: WG chairs, TF/task leads have difficulties to find time for WG activities and to engage WG members, so it is challenging to pursue collaborations and dialogue with other WGs or NCs. Activities planned to end at the end of October 2025, and option for resubmission is considered.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Coordination	WG benefits from effective planning, coordination and organisation of work (e.g. Google Drive)
Networks	WG benefits from building on strong already existing expert networks on the topic

Fig. 7 WG 6 Learning and adaptive management Table

7. Recognising and rewarding Peer Review

In recognition of CoARA Commitments 1 & 2 – the need to recognise the diversity of research contributions and the imperative to base research assessment primarily on qualitative assessments for which peer review is essential – the mission of this working group is to develop systematic approaches to increasing the visibility of, and according the appropriate recognition/reward to, peer review activities by the research community. This work of this group addresses the systematic and coordinated efforts required by both organisations that make use of peer review (e.g., scholarly publishers and research funders), as well as those that assess and reward researchers in research assessment processes (e.g., research performing- and research funding-organisations).

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are:

- Tung Tung Chan (Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam)
- Bernd Pulverer (EMBO Press)
- Johan Rooryck (cOAlition S)

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Set-up of subgroups (January 2024 – May 2024):** Following their kick-off meeting in November 2023, the working group set up three subgroups that began inventorising the current issues with the peer review of books, journal/scholarly articles, and funding proposals, researching and analysing the evidence to address the specific issues, and proposing distinctive/adaptable solutions in these 3 distinct areas (books, journal/scholarly articles, and funding proposals).
- First [draft](#) of **'Recognizing and rewarding peer review activities of scholarly articles, books, and funding proposals' (May 2024 – August 2024):** The draft recommendations provide a generalisable template for the responsibilities and actions required by key stakeholders to develop a systemic approach to recognising and rewarding peer review activities for scholarly manuscripts, books, and funding proposals within research assessment processes.
- **Open Consultation (August 2024 – January 2025):** The first draft was circulated for feedback among the whole WG, the wider CoARA community, and the wider research community in stages by sharing a [feedback form](#) on the draft recommendations.

- **Presentation of recommendations (November 2024 – present):** The (Co-)Chairs have been presenting the current iteration of the recommendations at various panels and events, such as the 2024 World Science Forum in Budapest.

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- Recommendations on **‘Recognizing and rewarding peer review activities of scholarly articles, books, and funding proposals’ (February 2025 – April 2025):** The (Co-)Chairs are addressing and incorporating the substantive feedback from the open consultation and expect to publish the final draft on Zenodo for wider public dissemination.
- **Pilots of recommendations (May 2025 – November 2025):** The working group is currently collecting different types of institutions to pilot the relevant recommendations voluntarily via this [form](#). This process will not be coordinated by the (Co-)Chairs, but rather by creating a shared platform where institutions can collaborate on the pilots, with some guidelines provided.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Symposium to share lessons from pilots (November 2025):** The working group aims to organise a conference where the piloting institutions can share early results and/or lessons from the pilots.

Narrative assessment:

The draft recommendations have received substantial feedback and incorporating the different suggestions at varying levels of detail is a long-drawn process. Furthermore, there are some questions on how to deal with feedback the authors disagree with – and what that means for when the recommendations are published. This is related to questions on what it means for an output to be (or not to be) endorsed by the CoARA community.

The Group also foresees questions on how to enable/facilitate/support the pilots and eventual implementation of the recommendations on recognising and rewarding peer review because this cannot be solely undertaken by the (Co-)Chairs or WG membership.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Incorporating Feedback	As mentioned above, there have been some capacity issues in dealing with feedback that the authors disagree with; the lesson has been that we respond/address comments but

	do not necessarily incorporate all requests.
Size of membership	<p>It has been important to keep the size of the WG small to enable some agility and efficiency.</p> <p>The key to managing requests for new joiners of CoARA to participate in the WG is to request them to consider piloting the recommendations.</p>
Administrative burden	The administrative obligations from CoARA could be simplified.

Fig. 8 WG 7 Learning and adaptive management Table

8. Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)

The mission of the WG Reforming Academic Career Assessment is to broaden the reflection on research assessment to ACA, taking into account the full range of work conducted by academics in research, teaching, learning, innovation, management, leadership, and service to society.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: *Pastora Martínez Samper (EUA)*, *Moniek Tromp (Young Academy of Europe)*, *Rita Morais (EUA & WG Coordinator)*

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Survey** on academic career assessment (October 2023 – April 2024) – gathering information on institutional/organisation level initiatives that aim to broaden the criteria and methods for evaluating the outputs and impacts of academic activities for the purposes of recruitment, performance evaluation and career progression of academic staff. The survey was developed by the members of the WG and a pilot was conducted with organisations from 10 countries. Survey and database: <https://zenodo.org/records/14548157>
- **Collection of case studies** on ACA (January – June 2024) – showcasing well-established international and national level initiatives for reforming research and academic career assessment. Eleven case studies were collected. The template for the case studies was developed by the WG ACA and it was subject to a pilot test, developed internally in the WG. Case studies: <https://zenodo.org/records/14548013>
- **Webinar** “Reforming Academic Career Assessment – CoARA Working Group” (4 March 2024) – goals, objectives and ongoing activities. Specifically, the efforts to map institutional and national initiatives dedicated to reforming academic career assessment were explored – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5KwMFdAKIkM&t=506s>
- **Workshop** “Reforming Academic Career Assessment: current insights and future directions” (25 June 2024) – This workshop highlighted the key outcomes from the WG ACA large-scale survey and case-studies, offering valuable insights into the current landscape of academic career assessment reforms. The input gathered in the discussions informed the development of an adaptable toolbox for academic career assessment. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4OIOF0bFSVU>
- **Report** on lessons learned, based on the outcomes of the survey and case studies, this document outlines important lessons and insights to help

institutions guide their reform processes (April – December 2024):
<https://zenodo.org/records/14548106>

Minor issues on outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **A draft toolbox** (October 2024 – February 2025). The WG aims to develop an adaptable toolbox for ACA, considering all university missions and the broad scope of activities, skills and competences of academic staff at different stages of their career. Slight delay.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Feasibility studies** (April – May 2025)
- **Final toolbox** (June – October 2025)

Narrative assessment:

The WG began its activities in October 2023. Members are organised into subgroups focusing on specific tasks, with participation in tasks and subgroups being voluntary.

Progress on the mapping exercise – including the survey, case-study collection, and lessons learned – has been slower than initially anticipated due to several factors. These include task complexity, resource constraints among WG members, and limited availability for meetings and work development. Despite these challenges, a core group of WG members has remained consistently active in the development of WG tasks.

Also important to mention that although many WG members have limited availability, they remain committed to the goals of the WG and continue to provide input as needed. Given these constraints, the WG has revised and adjusted the timeline of its activities, to ensure that the expected outcomes are delivered within the life cycle of the WG. However, it is very likely that limited resources from members will remain a challenge.

The WG would also benefit from increased synergies with other WGs and National Chapters.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Managerial and operational	Given the resource constraints of WG members (e.g. time, staff availability to work on different tasks), it has been necessary to allocate a longer time for the development of some tasks.

	Periods of consultation with WG members also cannot be too short, so as to allow for sufficient time for feedback.
Managerial and operational	The possibility to revise and re-structure the tasks initially outlined in the WG proposal and adapting them to be evolving work is positive.
Managerial and operational	In WGs with a large membership, ensuring active participation from most members can be challenging. Many members face resource constraints, such as limited time for meetings or a lack of operational resources needed to engage fully in tasks. Some members may join the group primarily to learn, which is also valuable. However, it may not be realistic to expect a high level of active participation from a large number of members.

Fig. 9 WG 8 Learning and adaptive management Table

9. Responsible metrics and indicators

The mission of the WG Responsible Metrics and Indicators is to critically evaluate current indicators currently employed in the evaluation of researchers, awards, institutional assessments, and the progression of scientific advancement with the aim of providing recommendations for reform. Information below is reported as of March 2025.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Felix Schönbrodt (Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München), Katarzyna Nawrot (University of Warsaw), Rachel Heyard (University of Zurich (UZH)), Davide Crepaldi (SISSA).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Assessing the status quo (Stage 1):** investigation of various institutions, disciplines and cultural contexts related to research assessments. [A survey](#) was developed and tested among WG members, and the final survey will be shared with all CoARA members and beyond in April 2025. The task is on track and started in October 2023.
- **Critical evaluation of the indicators and recommendations (Stage 2):** Based on the survey results, guiding questions and recommendations on when to use indicators will be developed, including suggestions on how to integrate them with qualitative assessment methods. The team used the pilot survey results to start developing an outline for the full text, which is still in progress. This stage started in November 2023 and is on track.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Strategic Plan for Dissemination (Stage 3):** This stage focuses on sharing findings, strategies, and recommendations with a wider audience, emphasizing their applicability across disciplines and cultures. This stage has not started yet.

Narrative assessment:

- **On the Questionnaire:** The pilot survey for Stage 1, "Assessing the Status Quo," was concluded, with a significant portion (30 institutions) of WG members participating. This survey helped move the process to Stage 2, "Critical Evaluation of Indicators and Recommendations." The team has been working on updating the survey before sending it to all CoARA members and beyond and right now the final version of the survey is undergoing tasting before being distributed in April 2025. The survey platform and questions were found to be

effective and scalable, though efforts have been made to reduce its length to prevent discouraging members from completing it. The aim was to categorize 75 indicators for research assessment gathered from members in the pilot survey in terms of character of their impact, quality and quantity.

- **On the Recommendation Document:** The team initiated the development of a recommendation document with the help of experts in scientific consensus building. A brainstorming event in November 2023 led to the creation of a "brainstorming document" where ideas and suggestions were collected. A Writing Team is now being appointed to extract key points and work on the draft of the document. The process will be transparent, with multiple opportunities for the entire WG and affiliated experts to contribute feedback and refine the drafts at various stages.

Selected Talks and Presentations during 2024:

1. Nawrot K.A., 12.12.2024, "Reforms on advancing research assessment: Responsible Metrics and Indicators", RAEG meeting, Brno (online).
2. Nawrot K.A., 29.10.2024, "Direction of responsible use of metrics and indicators – preliminary findings from the research of Responsible Metrics and Indicators Working Group of CoARA", 4th FAIR Implementation Workshop, „Reform of research assessment“, EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT (online).
3. Nawrot K.A., 22.10.2024, "[Open Science and Non-Bibliometric Aspects of Research Evaluation and Assessment](#)," participation in an expert panel, University of Łódź, Łódź.
4. Nawrot K.A., 11.09.2024, "Responsible Metrics and Indicators Working Group – challenges and opportunities", CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) WG Co-Chairs Forum: Connecting Efforts, Helsinki, Finland.
5. Nawrot K.A., 14.05.2024, „Responsible metrics and indicators“, 2nd FAIR Implementation Workshop, „Assessing national current FAIR-enabling capabilities“, EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT (online).

Learning and adaptive management

Topic	Lessons learned
Voluntary work	Even though the steering group and many members are really intrinsically motivated, the amount of voluntary work that can be dedicated to this WG is limited. The Group could not really use the support from the CoARA Boost project (except one small financial contribution). Often, the WG realised "Oh, this actually is a full-blown

	research project that would need funding and a dedicated person focusing on this task”, and searched for ways to scale it to a doable scope.
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Fig. 10 WG 9 Learning and adaptive management Table

10. Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance (SAGA)

In biomedical institutions, research assessments are highly regulated and procedurally institutionalised. Administrative reform is a crucial part of sustainable and successful research assessment reforms (RAR).

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Miriam Kip (Charité) and Iris Uribealgo (EU-LIFE).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities from the WG:

- **Documentation** of monthly group meetings (minutes) and slides (November 2023–present, internal). It also includes the results of a MIRO board exercise to identify relevant areas of research assessment, which was the basis for an Open Virtual Brainstorming Event with relevant stakeholders and expert talks (see below).
- **Open Virtual Brainstorming Event** (May 2024): a two-day event with international relevant stakeholders and expert talks. It was a call to action for professionals, especially those working in the administration and governance of research institutions, to engage in an international co-creation process to develop a white paper for a feasible action plan template to equip research institutions with knowledge and strategies to implement changes in their respective research evaluation systems and organisational processes.
- **Case studies descriptions** compiled with the presentations during the Open Virtual Brainstorming Event (May–June 2024, see above).
- **Collaborative writing session** (July 2024) held in Berlin for 3 days with members of the CoARA WG SAGA. Based on the discussions and expertise within the WG, and the input from the Open Virtual Brainstorming Event, this session was aimed at co-creating the first draft of the above-mentioned white paper for an action plan template.

Completed outputs/activities from individual members of the WG with a focus on the topic of the WG and CoARA:

- **Selected Talks and Poster Presentations during 2025:**
 - Structured narrative CVs in the Lifesciences (2025). Workshop Mutual Learning Experience. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024303>.
 - Matters of Research Assessment and Its Implementation (MAI) – Part: Implementation Status Quo (2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024263>.

- Incentives and Research Assessment Reforms (2025). Introduction to the topic. AG Hennemuth, Deutsches Herzzentrum Berlin. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15023262>.
 - Incentives and Research Assessment Reforms (2025). Introduction to the topic. AG Sittinger, Charité.
 - Efforts to undermine DEI in Science and HEI – how to respond to it effectively? Journal Club (DRIVERS), online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15023173>.
 - OPEN MERIT - CoARA aligned activities at Charité and BIH. Berlin University Alliance (BUA) CoARA Coordinators meeting Feb 2025.
 - Presentación y primeros pasos del GT2 Criterios de Evaluación. Encuentro de grupos de trabajo de National Chapter Spain (February 2025)
 - Upcoming information session “The new research group evaluation system at IDIBAPS: a Cancer research area pilot” (May 2025)
- **Selected Talks and Poster Presentations during 2024:**
- Perspectives from the Perspectives project: peer-review as a vehicle to explore the scientific publishing landscape, improve quality and strengthen methods competencies (2024). [METRICS International Forum Stanford](#).
 - CoARA Boost 2024: TREASURE - Rewarding early-stage researchers for implementing reproducible, reusable and open research. General Council of the CoARA National Chapter – Portugal, January 15, 2025, online.
 - TREASURE: Rewarding graduate students for implementing open science. CiBB Science Fair Meeting, December 20, 2024, Lousã, Portugal.
 - Advancing research assessment at UC: Implementing and rewarding open science and responsible research practices. CERES – 30 years anniversary: Annual meeting, December 19, 2024, Coimbra, Portugal.
 - Why open science and responsible research training of early career researchers matters. Meta-research in sport science workshop, December 12, 2024, Coimbra, Portugal.
 - From theory to practice - Implementing best practice in research assessment systems through infrastructure (2024) QUEST Seminar on Responsible Research, online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15023194>
 - CoARA at Charité and BIH. (2024). Research Commission Charité. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15020274>
 - BIH Indicator Working Group. Repeated faculty meetings in 2024 – 2025. Leadership: Prod. Duda, Prof. Baum, Dr. Kathrin Haubold, Berlin Institute of Health.

- From theory to practice -Implementing best practice in research assessment systems through infrastructure. (2024). Lunch talk – BUA OS Ambassador Meeting.
 - Incentives and Research Assessment Reforms (2024). Introduction to the topic. AG Guillot. Charité.
 - Research Assessment Reforms – From theory to practice: MERIT Portal for professorial appointments at Charité (2024). CoARA National Chapter Germany Public Meeting. Bonn
 - Changing research incentives in practice: lessons from institutional experiments (2024). CERN-NASA Working Group "Incentives for Open Scholarship". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11444251>
 - Good Assessment Practice and CoARA (2024). Presentation to representatives of the Helmholtz Society. Berlin.
 - Advancing Research Assessment. Poster Presentation STEM – [Women in Science Conference 2024. Berlin.](#)
 - Incentives and Research Assessment Reforms (2024). Introduction to the Topic. Center for Anesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine (CC7), Charité.
 - From Theory to Practice – Implementing Responsible Research Assessments & Open Science Incentives (2024). BIH Breakfast Seminar. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822252>
 - From theory to practice - Impulse Forschungsbewertung (2024). Workshop Charité BIH Innovation. Berlin. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15043752>
 - Open Science Incentives and Research Assessment Reforms (2024). Berlin I Oxford Summer School 2024. <https://osf.io/p5v4b/>
 - Advancing Research Assessment for Incentives (2024). Frühjahrstreffen FG Datenbanken. Jena. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15055404>
- **Selected Talks and Poster Presentations during 2023:**
- CoARA Working group – Presentation to EUHA Research Leads Network (RLN) (2023) Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024829>
 - Research Assessment at BUA Kooperation mit BUA Innovationsgruppe [“Matters of Research Assessment”](#) (Cornelia Schendzielorz, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; Miriam Kip, Berlin Institute of Health @Charité) (2023).
 - Reformen in der Forschungsbewertung – Herausforderungen und Chancen für das Berufungsmanagement (2023). 4. Netzwerktagung Berufungsmanagement, Universität Hamburg. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14964840>
 - Matters of Research Assessment and its Implementation - Part: Implementation (2023). Abschlussworkshop BUA Open Science Dashboards. Berlin

- Implementing Responsible Research Assessments for Appointments at the BUA – No Chance without Collaborations. BIH Scientific Symposium 2023: "Sparking Collaborations in Health Research", Berlin. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10821717>
- **Panel Participation:**
 - Participant ["Open Science incentives and institutional change"](#) LMU & MPG Open Science Summer School on Friday (13.09.24).
 - Host: ["EVALUATING RESEARCHERS: AMBITIONS AND REALITIES"](#), during the Berlin Science Week:
 - Upcoming: "Helmholtz Reproducibility Workshop" Roundtable on March 25th at 13:30 ["Round table: Reproducibility in Research Assessment: Shaping transparent and measurable health research"](#)
- **Workshop/Event participation**
 - [Workshop on Structured narrative CVs in the Lifesciences – a mutual learning experience between Early Career and Mid/Senior Career Researchers. \(2025\).](#)
 - Virtual Brainstorm' to develop the 'Action Plan' for the implementation of the CoARA principles on research assessment reforms at Charité and BIH: Day 1 and Day 2. (2024).
 - Discussion sessions of the IDIBAPS-CoARA working group (October 2023 and May 2024)
- **Tools**
 - [MERIT Portal: a comprehensive software for the application, management and assessment of professorial appointments at Charité and BIH.](#)
 - MERIT Structured narrative CV Builder: an [open tool](#) to practice and learn about structure narrative CVs in the life sciences.
 - New institutional system for the evaluation of research groups: comprehensive ARRA-aligned evaluation system for intramural assessment of research groups at IDIBAPS
- **Media**
 - Public Radio Germany: Simply the best? [Nachwuchsförderung im Wissenschaftsbetrieb.](#)

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Finalisation** of a comprehensive action plan template for administration and governance, initiated during the collaborative writing session in Berlin (see

above, July 2024– present), based on the activities and results from the CoARA WG SAGA.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Conference/workshop** with relevant stakeholders upon finalisation of the action plan template, including the role of administration and governance in advancing research assessment reforms in alignment with CoARA. The content gathered may feed into further outputs/actions (tbd).

Narrative assessment:

Process-Related Aspects:

- The WG has been meeting monthly for an hour over the past year, but the effectiveness of this frequency remains unclear.
- Active participation is complex, with discussions often driven by a few members. However, smaller, focused meetings (e.g., for event planning) have been more engaging.
- Creating a participatory and co-creative environment requires balancing structured discussions and open knowledge exchange.
- A key challenge is maintaining a focus on administration, science management, and governance in research assessment reforms, as discussions often shift towards research practices from a researcher's perspective.
- The lack of visibility and recognition of CoARA activities within institutions and CoARA itself limits motivation for voluntary participation.
- Additional administrative duties and reporting requirements imposed by CoARA add to the workload, making participation more burdensome.
- Uncertainty about CoARA's direction, as the initial focus on institutional policy implementation appears to be shifting towards status analyses and survey research.

Output/Outcome Level:

- The working group aims to provide guidance on enacting policies within the implementation cycle of research assessment reforms.
- By leveraging in-depth institutional insights and focusing on administration and governance roles, the group hopes to offer valuable, generalizable implementation guidance.
- Their efforts seek to bridge the gap between policy discussions and actual implementation, contributing to actionable reforms.

Learning and adaptive management

Topic	Lessons learned
Keeping focus on the topic	Consequent guidance and reminders, providing thematic structure for each meeting can help.
Onboarding of new members	The group developed a structured on boarding process to support new members to be able to catch up with the status of the ongoing discussions and on deliverables.
Balancing input, burden and success	Discuss and balance workload that is not-oriented towards the original goals of implementation of research assessment reform.

Fig. 11 WG 10 Learning and adaptive management Table

II. Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research (TIER)

The mission of the WG TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research is to identify and take into account systematic biases that may be present in evaluation criteria, as well as accidental confirmation biases that may arise among evaluators.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Silvia Penati, University of Milano-Bicocca (Chair), Bonaria Biancu, University of Milano-Bicocca (Deputy Chair), Jasmine Lorenzini, SNSF, and Arianna Montorsi, Polytechnic University of Turin, ((Co-)Chairs of TF1), Lucio Pisacane, IRPPS-CNR, and Giuliana Rubbia, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, ((Co-)Chairs of TF2).

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Template for national case studies** to present data on national databases and evaluation approaches in RFOs and RPOs (June 2024)

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Summary of the five case studies** to highlight common challenges and identified best practices (July 2024 – October 2024) – almost completed (90%)
- Regular meetings to organise and supervise the work on TF1 (May 2024 to November 2024)
- Selection of **training videos** to address bias in evaluation of research (May 2024 to November 2024 – almost completed). [The videos](#) are designed to educate and raise awareness about implicit bias and gender parity in research assessment, while also giving practical solutions.
- **Survey** to individuals from CoARA members to identify perceptions of gender and intersectional biases in research evaluation and assessment procedures (October – May 2025). Targets are research performing organizations and funding agencies. The aim is to understand current practices and bias issues to recommend more equitable methods (best practices/mitigation strategies).
- **Report of the in-person meeting held on February 7, 2025.** It highlights key messages for a bias-free research assessment that emerged from invited speeches, presentations and discussions among TIER participants. To be disseminated extensively on various channels and shared with stakeholders and other WGs (additional output, on track).

Narrative assessment:

The WG TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research – was approved by the COARA Steering Board in February 2024, in the second round of approvals. Activities started officially at the Kick-off Meeting on March 22, 2024, eleven months by now. Due to the delay in the approval, TIER is about five months behind the other WGs in its project accomplishment.

At the kick-off meeting the organizational structure of the WG was approved, and the (Co-)Chairs of Task Force 1 (TF1) and Task Force 2 (TF2) were appointed. One of the two (Co-)Chairs of TF2 was later replaced, due to unexpected unavailability of the former one.

The Action Plan was finalised at the end of May 2024. Communication and Interaction Plan, together with Data Management Plan were approved at the end of June 2024.

TF1 has been carrying on a collection of available data on the gender distribution in academic and research positions, as well as on best practices to mitigate bias in evaluation, already implemented in different countries. This has been conducted on five case studies (Finland, Italy, Switzerland, UK, EU Commission), by providing a general template (Output n. 1) to be filled with information at national level for the four involved countries, plus EU commission. Some National Chapters have been playing a crucial role in completing this step. This activity should end in May 2025, but a preliminary summary is already available (Output n. 2). Outputs 1 and 2 will eventually merge into the final deliverable D1 of the Action Plan.

TF2 has been conducting a general landscape of the relevant literature regarding the problem of bias distortions in evaluation procedures. This activity will last until the end of 2024. A report will be drafted by then. This landscape will be completed by a catalogue of open access tools (videos, online training courses, etc..) to counteract bias in assessment and evaluation procedures, already available online. A still partial collection of tools can be found in Output 3.

TF1 together with TF2 and the rest of the TIER community have just finished to draft the text of a first survey (Output n. 4) on the perception of the presence of biases in evaluation and assessment procedures, to be provided to individuals of the CoARA community at different career stages, from PhD students to research staff. The submission of this survey was planned for the beginning of December 2024, but it was ready to be disseminated in early February 2025, after several revisions. The revisions accounted for various issues emerging from open discussions within TIER participants and aimed at a version as inclusive as possible, informative enough

and anonymous. In February 2025, it was finally sent to the Secretariat for dissemination to all CoARA representatives. By the end of March, the WG expects to complete data collection, and then analyze them and present results in May 2025. If the number of survey participants is not sufficient, the Group will consider postponing the response deadline and expanding the target audience to include institutions outside CoARA, making greater use of platforms such as social networks.

A second survey on best practices against bias applied by the COARA institutions is under preparation and will be submitted to all CoARA members in 2025. A preliminary version has been tested within TIER members, looking for ranking of best practices (February 2025).

TIER has monthly meetings. Up to now the Group have organised eight meetings preceded by restricted meetings only for (Co-)Chairs. In addition, TF1 and TF2 have regular operational meetings to carry on their own activities. Monthly meetings are well received, with an average number of 20–25 people attending every time. Any meeting is recorded and rolling minutes are provided. This appears very useful to track the work in progress.

TF2 performed various communication actions and external engagement to share awareness of TIER work in progress. TIER Chair Silvia Penati has been invited to present TIER activities at:

- Slovenia workshop “Gender perspective integration and evaluation in research” (27 March 2024, online)
- ERA Action 5 subgroup meeting (23 May 2024, online)
- MINDtheGEPs and Elsevier Open Forum roundtable “*Equality in Focus: Steps Towards Inclusive Progress*” (27 November 2024, online)
- Donne e Scienza Conference of the Italian Women in Science Association with a session dedicated to research assessment (Genoa, 10 Dec 2024).
- GENDERACTION+ final Conference (Brussels, 11–12 February 2025).
- ITRN IV Annual Congress, the annual congress of the Italian Reproducibility Network (Milano, 13 February 2025).
-

A new logo has been conceived and proposed, showing two hands holding a stylised planet, to evoke inclusion and sustainability (February 2025); CoARA Communication Officer, Katrina Gibbs, accepted it and will use it when updating TIER webpage.

Since January 2025, two events have been submitted through the dedicated submission page “Submit to the CoARA Newsletter and update WG+NC Webpages”, advertising the first in-person meeting of February 7, 2025, and a

preview of the Survey on Bias perception for CoARA members. They appeared on the CoARA February 5 Newsletter and the TIER webpage.

TIER organised an in-person meeting on February 7, 2025 open to all TIER members (Output n. 5). Partial financial support from CoARA Boost was used. The meeting was also open to remote attendance. In total, about 35 TIER members participated, with 22 people in presence.

TIER activities are tailored to dig out and mitigate gender bias in evaluation and its intersection with other sources of bias. However, while data regarding gender distribution in research and the effects of gender bias on it are easy to collect, there is a severe lack of data regarding other kinds of bias. This may compromise a complete overview of biases in evaluation and research assessment.

Data concerning gender distribution in research are often available only as aggregated data (elaborations and statistics), the access to raw data being prevented. The Group is presently in contact with the head of the gender sector in the EU Commission to obtain anonymous raw data at EU level.

Since its approval, the TIER WG has been quite unbalanced in the geographical distribution of its members and kind of institutions (RPOs vs RFOs). Though this problem is going to be partially mitigated by the addition of new members, it may skew the distribution of available data and the kind of insights that will be shared. Mitigation will be obtained by purposely reaching CoARA people and institutions, also outside TIER.

WG activities are conducted by researchers on a voluntary basis, most of the time without any official institutional recognition. The presence of higher-priority commitments related to research, teaching and other institutional activities, together with lack of dedicated resources may prevent TIER from being always on track with the Action Plan. A scale back from the original proposal will be likely necessary, unless the WG deadline is going to be postponed or the possibility to apply for a renewal of the WG will be open by the CoARA Steering Committee.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Active involvement of TIER members	It can be difficult to actively involve TIER members in the WG activities, primarily due to higher-priority commitments related to research, teaching and institutional duties. Fractionating WG activities into small and temporal well-

		defined tasks helps get more people involved.
Interactions and synergies with other WGs		Any revision of general criteria for research assessment has to include the bias dimension. Therefore, it is important for TIER to WGs interact with the activities of the other WGs. The Group has learnt how to implement interactions through the appointment of mutual observers. The in-person (Co-)Chairs meeting in Helsinki helped in this perspective.
National Chapters		Constant interactions with National Chapters have proved to be very useful, in particular at the stage of data collection
Time schedule and resources		People work for TIER WG on a voluntary basis without relevant resources and/or institutional recognition. Being committed to other funded activities, the fraction of time that they can devote to TIER activities is restricted. The problem has been partially mitigated by hiring a collaborator financially supported by University of Milano-Bicocca. Nevertheless, a complete accomplishment of all the tasks declared in the original proposal might be unachievable and the Action Plan might require a partial revision.
CoARA Boost support		The possibility for WGs to apply to the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme should be considered.

Fig. 12 WG 11 Learning and adaptive management Table

12. Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment (OI4RRA)

Effective research assessment shapes funding decisions, academic careers, and ultimately, scientific progress. Yet, traditional research evaluation models – built on closed, proprietary systems and narrow, publication-based metrics – fail to capture the full range of research contributions to knowledge, policy, and society. This Working Group’s mission is to advocate for and facilitate the transition away from closed, proprietary infrastructure and research information to open, transparent, and interoperable infrastructures to support responsible research assessment (RRA).

In the first year, the focus of the working group is on establishing a shared understanding of Open Infrastructures (OI), identifying challenges and opportunities through landscape analyses and interviews, and developing frameworks, including architecture, policies, and schemas. The second year transitions to adoption and operationalisation by creating practical use cases, training guidelines, and recommendations for policymakers and research leaders. It also explores sustainable business models and governance structures to ensure long-term adoption, scalability, and alignment with emerging research assessment practices.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE AMKE), Clifford Tatum (CWTS –Leiden University)

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework Report** (February 2024 – February 2025): This report defines the principles and characteristics that are essential for an Open Infrastructure (OI) for responsible research assessment (RRA). Following the publication of the first draft on Zenodo, it was circulated for [feedback](#) to the other CoARA WG through an email campaign, as well as to the CoARA National Chapters, and to the wider CoARA community by publishing the call for feedback in the CoARA newsletter, on LinkedIn, and the ‘News’ section on the CoARA website. Two consultation webinars were held to discuss the framework and collect feedback – the slides and recordings from the public consultation sessions are available [here](#). After the consultation is completed, the feedback received will be integrated into the Report and be published in April 2025.

- **Institutional Interviews** (October 2024 – February 2025): The WG conducted interviews with 13 institutions and a total of 17 expert stakeholders, all of whom have either adopted or are in the process of transitioning to OI for RRA. These interviews aim to gather best practices, challenges, recommendations and insights to inform the WG's outputs.
- **Personas (May 2024 – July 2024)**: The WG produced personas to represent the wide spectrum of stakeholders in order to illustrate the challenges in traditional research assessment and thereby highlight the benefits of OI tools.

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework Report (April 2025)**: The final report will be published in April 2025.
- **Checklists (March 2025 – May 2025)**: Drawing on insights from the *Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework Report*, the working group is developing comprehensive checklists. These tools are designed to empower decision-makers in research-performing and research-funding organisations to transition efficiently and effectively to an open infrastructure for responsible research assessment.
- **A report on the institutional interviews** (January 2025 – June 2025): The report will synthesise findings from the institutional interviews to provide insights into the best practices, challenges, and lessons learned, which will inform future guidelines and tools by the WG.
- **Conceptual Architecture for the Implementation of a Responsible Research Assessment Framework Built on Open Infrastructures** (March 2024 – June 2025): The working group is developing a guide for the implementation of an RRA framework built on OI that addresses the technical, legal, and financial capacities required. This strategic framework aims to help institutions create transparent, equitable, and effective research evaluation underpinned by OI. This conceptual framework will be augmented with **policy briefs** (June 2025) targeted at policymakers to support OI at the legislative level.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Business and governance plan**: This output will produce a comprehensive report that analyses various business models and governance structures for OIs for RRA, offering clear recommendations and including a draft charter for a coordination body if deemed necessary.
- **Recommendations for training programmes**: Designed for policy makers and research executives, this output focuses on the development of targeted training programmes that pinpoint key audiences, identify awareness gaps, and suggest

effective implementation structures, while also outlining clear guidelines for decision-makers and investors on using and investing in OI.

Narrative assessment:

The working group's workplan is organised into five key stages:

1. Understanding focuses on defining concepts, mapping the landscape, and identifying enablers.
2. Specifications detail the components, interconnections, principles, and descriptions required for implementation.
3. Adoption emphasises fostering cultural change, addressing financial barriers, and building supportive structures.
4. Transition centres on standardisation, integration, governance, and ensuring long-term sustainability.
5. Operationalisation delivers actionable recommendations, develops business models, and establishes effective management and coordination mechanisms to ensure smooth execution.

WG OI4RRA has made substantial advancements in executing its workplan. Key milestones include:

- **Publication and Public Consultation:** [The Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework](#) has been published, with public consultation currently underway.
- **Institutional Interviews and Report Development:** Interviews with institutions transitioning to OI are complete, and the report is in the finalisation stage. This report will inform on the enablers and challenges on the transition towards OI for RRA, and will provide a set of recommendations for stakeholders.
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- **Conceptual Architecture:** A conceptual architecture detailing the technical, legal, and financial capacities required for Open Infrastructure adoption has been established, with further refinements in progress.
- **Stakeholder Personas and User Stories:** Development has been successfully completed, emphasising the limitations of traditional metrics and illustrating how the schema addresses these challenges.

Challenges and Mitigation Strategies :

- **Stakeholder Feedback Integration:** Synthesising diverse perspectives into a cohesive framework remains a challenge. Engagement mechanisms are being developed to enhance coherence and applicability.
- **Recognition of Diverse Contributions:** Advocacy efforts continue to push for broader acceptance of varied research outputs in assessment methodologies.
- **Interview Participation:** Securing participants for institutional interviews has been challenging due to scheduling conflicts and unresponsiveness.

Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Members' engagement	It remains challenging to encourage WG members to actively contribute and co-produce outputs. While members express interest and support for the workstream's goals, competing priorities and limited availability often result in difficulties securing their direct input. This has underscored the need for more tailored approaches to engagement, such as breaking down tasks into smaller, manageable contributions and providing clearer guidance on how members can effectively participate. Encouraging co-production requires ongoing effort to foster a sense of shared ownership and accountability among members.

Fig. 13 WG 12 Learning and adaptive management Table

13. Towards Transformations:

The mission of the WG Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts is to align three distinct yet interconnected streams of activities towards transformations with the aim to generate societal impacts.

The **(Co-)Chairs** of this WG are: Prof. Dr. Marc Wolfram (Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development), Prof. Dr. Josefin Wangel (FORMAS), Martin Jaekel (Zurich university of Applied Sciences- ZHAW), Dr. Thomas Brunotte (Hochschullehrbund hlb), Prof. Dr. Raimund Bleischwitz (Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research ZMT), Prof. Dr. Teresa Sordé Martí (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona)

13.1. Transdisciplinary Research SG

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- Monthly **meetings**: Partner Workshops
- Creation of **Internal Glossary** (December 2023 – March 2024).
- Creation of WG SG's **collaborative space** on Zotero (February 2024).
- **Mapping exercise**: "Learning from Reference Case: Challenges and Solutions for Transdisciplinary Research (Assessment)" (March 2024 – April 2024).
- Scoping **review** of transdisciplinary assessment literature (May 2024 – August 2024).

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Collection** of relevant TDR assessment literature (ongoing)
- **Document**: "Reference base and challenges for TD assessment" and "Reference base and challenges for TD assessment" (August 2024 – February 2025)
- Creation and distribution of stakeholder **survey** and potential workshops (October 2024 – December 2024). The survey is meant to distribute to relevant non-scientific TDR stakeholders who have participated in TDR projects.
- **Drafting** of Transdisciplinary Quality Criteria (November 2024 – March 2025)
- Completion of the first **draft** of "CoARA guidelines for assessing excellence in transdisciplinary research" (August 2025).
- The **final report** "CoARA guidelines for assessing excellence in transdisciplinary research", completed and published (December 2025).

To start outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Review** of Stakeholder Study (March 2025) – a qualitative analysis of the stakeholder surveys, to further fuel WG SG's guidance and recommendations.
- Drafting **guidance** for TDR related policies, programs, and calls (March 2025 – June 2025).
- Drafting **guidance** for TDR related proposal, process, outputs, outcomes, impacts – Recommendations for research funders on how to support and assess TDR proposal, process, outputs, outcomes and impacts (March 2025 – June 2025).
- **Validation Workshop** – in person in Brussels, to discuss the "CoARA guidelines for assessing excellence in transdisciplinary research" (October 2025).
- **Circulation and dissemination** of the guidelines (December 2025).

Narrative assessment:

The Working Group Subgroup Transdisciplinary Research (WG SG TDR) has made significant strides toward achieving its objectives, as evidenced by the progress across multiple outputs, deliverables, and activities. Early efforts focused on establishing foundational structures and resources, such as the creation of a collaborative glossary to define key working terms, which was successfully shared and expanded upon internally. This glossary has ensured clarity and alignment within the group.

A major milestone was the establishment of the WG SG's collaborative space on Zotero, which now serves as a central repository for meeting minutes, upcoming events, working documents, and a comprehensive library of over 200 suggested literature items. The collection, contributed by WG SG members and external stakeholders, has undergone a rigorous scoping review. All abstracts were read, and relevant articles were studied in detail, culminating in the consolidation of insights into an internal document, "Reference Base and Challenges for TD Assessment." This document is actively shaping the group's forthcoming guidelines.

The group has also held several Partner Workshops (PWs) to facilitate collaboration, plan processes, and refine deliverables. These workshops are well-documented, with minutes circulated promptly to ensure transparency and alignment. To date, ten PWs have been completed, addressing various stages of the project, including the review of the scoping literature and drafting of quality criteria for TDR assessment.

To broaden perspectives, the WG SG has designed and is currently about to distribute a stakeholder survey targeting non-scientific TDR stakeholders. This survey seeks to understand how these stakeholders see quality in TDR projects and to capture their experiences of evaluating/assessing TDR projects. Results from this

exercise, along with other mapping efforts such as "Learning from Reference Cases: Challenges and Solutions for TDR Assessment," are being used to inform both the drafting of TDR quality criteria and the development of comprehensive guidance.

Looking ahead, the group is on track to deliver key outcomes. The drafting of TDR quality criteria is progressing, with smaller meetings planned to finalise these recommendations. Guidance for TDR-related policies, programs, and calls, as well as TDR proposals, processes, outputs, outcomes, and impacts, will be drafted in tandem. Milestone PWs are scheduled to review these drafts, ensuring robust feedback and refinement.

The validation workshop, a critical in-person event, is planned for September/October 2024 in Brussels. This workshop will integrate diverse stakeholder feedback and finalise the draft "CoARA Guidelines for Assessing Excellence in TD Research." The final guidelines will be completed and published by December 2024, followed by a targeted dissemination strategy leveraging CoARA's National Chapters and broader networks to maximise reach and impact.

In summary, the WG SG is making steady progress across all planned activities, with many key activities already completed or on track. The group's systematic and collaborative approach is ensuring the development of robust and actionable guidelines for transdisciplinary research assessment.

13.2. Applied/Practice-Based Research SG

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Completed outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Workshop 2:** Identification of existing relevant background for the assessment of regional economic impact assessment and new candidate assessment approaches for applied research – Collection of case studies across the working group and discussion of the lessons learned (October 2024).
- **Publication** of insights from Workshop 1 in a podcast and in "[Die neue Hochschule](#)"

Ongoing outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Publication** of insights from Workshop 2.

Minor issues with outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Workshop 1:** Identification of existing relevant background for the assessment of societal impact assessment and new candidate assessment approaches for applied research (June 2024) – minor issue: **report** delayed but now well

advanced (first draft is ready, there will be a group meeting in April to discuss following steps)

Narrative assessment:

The SG has been very dynamic and has a very clear focus and very relevant members that can push the reflection beyond the usual level. The SG has also been successful in involving researchers as well as experts on research assessment. The workplan has been executed meticulously and has generated great interest. The SG is now in the phase of discussing the results of the two workshops and deciding on the next steps. In addition, the members are agreeing on a concept on how to integrate the results of the 3 subgroups.

13.3. Societal Impacts SG

Outputs/deliverables/activities included in this WG:

Minor issues with outputs/deliverables/activities:

- A **white paper** on societal impact assessment (July 2024 – January 2025) – possibly with CoARA endorsement – A comprehensive report that synthesises best practices, debates and concerns on societal impact assessment of research and included semi-quantitative assessment on societal impact definition and implementation. The completion of the white paper has been delayed due to the limited time available for members to work on the white paper.

Future outputs/deliverables/activities:

- **Impact report** with interview results, evidence on selected pilots, and learnings (Mid 2025 – to start after the white paper). The report will consist of information on progress and outputs from pilot testing the framework.
- **Final framework** disseminated at a high-level meeting (winter 2025 – 2026) – a framework for evaluating the diversity of societal impacts that has been updated, tested and reviewed – to start in the 2nd half of 2025.

Narrative assessment:

The Societal Impact Group has made notable progress in advancing its objectives. By mid-November 2024, the group organised two online meetings and one in-person meeting in Brussels on 24 May 2024, providing a platform to discuss current practices, methodologies, concerns, and best practices for assessing societal impacts. These discussions have informed the development of a white paper synthesizing best practices and debates on societal impact assessments, which is expected to be finalised by early 2025. Additionally, the group has grown

significantly, with membership exceeding 60 individuals following the submission of similar proposals on societal impact to CoARA in mid-2024. This expansion reflects increasing recognition of societal impact as a critical component of research assessment.

WG TT: Learning and adaptive management:

Topic	Lessons learned
Managing growth and engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Since the launch of the CoARA WGs, the WG has received frequent inquiries (monthly) from individuals and organisations seeking to join our group. While this ongoing interest is highly encouraging, the onboarding process requires dedicated time and effort to integrate new members effectively. • Large WGs require significant time investments not only to complete tasks but also to maintain strong internal communication. The structure of our WG, consisting of three subgroups with over 50 contributing organisations, underscores the need for clear coordination mechanisms to ensure alignment across efforts. • The presence of dedicated coordinators (besides (Co-)Chairs) has significantly improved the efficiency and effectiveness of managing these large groups.
CoARA: Integration and connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The multitude of dimensions of research assessment currently addressed by CoARA risks leading to contradictions between the finding of different reform suggestions. A more structured approach to reforming research assessment (e.g. prioritisation of dimensions, integration of WGs, harmonisation of levels of reform suggestions) is urgently necessary. • While the WG has maintained internal communication within our WG subgroups, ensuring connectivity with other CoARA WGs remains a challenge. Given overlapping thematic areas, greater transparency on initiatives and deliverables from other groups would enhance cross-group collaboration. • The reliance on ad-hoc exchanges and one-on-one updates, while helpful, is resource-intensive. A structured, centralised, top-down approach to sharing

	information across WGs could facilitate more efficient engagement.
Balancing member motivation, time and capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The enthusiasm and commitment of our WG members are critical to our success. However, time constraints remain a persistent challenge. • Monthly meetings have proven effective in maintaining engagement, allowing flexibility for members to participate at different times. • Detailed minutes and personalised follow-ups via email have helped keep members informed and connected to ongoing work. • In-person meetings have proven highly effective in deepening discussions and strengthening relationships. Future planning should prioritise opportunities for face-to-face engagement where feasible, with additional budgetary support from CoARA to enable participation from a broader range of partners.

Fig. 14 WG 13 Learning and adaptive management Table

5. Co-Chairs Forums

(Co-)Chairs Forums are meetings (hybrid or online) involving the (Co-)Chairs of active WGs, aiming to: (i) facilitate information exchange among (Co-)Chairs regarding WG activities and progress; (ii) prevent duplication of efforts and encourage synergies across WGs; and (iii) foster mutual learning among participants. While these forums are generally scheduled biannually (aligned with CoARA General Assemblies, as agreed during the first forum), their frequency can be adjusted to accommodate evolving needs of the WGs, the CoARA Steering Board, and the CoARA Secretariat.

The preparation of the meetings includes calendar invites and informational emails containing a draft agenda and the preparation materials (i.e., a PowerPoint template presentation).

During these meetings, each WG (Co-)Chair provides a brief presentation on their group's progress. Dedicated time is allocated for discussion to promote mutual learning and identify potential synergies among the WGs. Additionally, (Co-)Chairs are encouraged to regularly upload their progress reports and outputs to the CoARA SharePoint, ensuring these materials remain accessible to all WGs in favor of connectivity.

So far, two (Co)-Chairs meetings have been held (a third one had been planned but was cancelled by petition of Co-Chairs, see below). The first one took place on the 17th of November 2023. The agenda and minutes are included in Annex 1 of this document. This first meeting laid the basis for the functioning of the Forums.

The second was hybrid and took place in Helsinki, Finland, facilitated by the Finnish Federation of Learned Societies on September 10-11th, 2024. The agenda and conclusions of the meeting are summarised in [this CoARA article](#). In the first part of the event, the Co-Chairs of the 13 WGs shared status updates with one another based on some key questions shared in advance.

Following the presentations, the afternoon session provided an open forum for discussion among WGs, fostering dialogue on operational and strategic matters for their future activities. Discussions emphasised connectivity among WGs and highlighted several overarching themes, including institutional and community recognition, strategies to address limited resources, strengthening connections between WGs and National Chapters, providing reliable resources to support the coalition's institutional reform efforts, and streamlining WG activities across transversal thematic areas.

Karen Stroobants (Steering Board) then presented a proposal on the first ideas for the WGs' Endorsement Framework and gathered feedback from (Co-)Chairs. The final version of the endorsement framework is included in D4.2 (revision of the Operational Framework).

During the hybrid meeting, key dates were also discussed. On the one hand, the dates regarding the submission of the progress reports, as part of WG self-assessment. The Monitoring Framework enables WGs to keep track of the progress and lessons learned for outputs and facilitates connectivity with other WGs by its sharing on a common SharePoint.

As stated in section 2 (Methodology), the submission deadlines for WG progress reports are the following.

- **1st report: 31 October 2024** – postponed to 31st of November in order to grant (Co-)Chairs more time to comment on the monitoring report template and accommodate changes.
- **2nd report: 31 October 2025**
- **3rd report: 31 October 2026**

On the other hand, the remaining (Co-)Chairs Forum dates were also shared and discussed. As agreed with the CoARA Secretariat, and announced during the Helsinki Forum, the meetings in November will be held hybrid. This method increases engagement and linkage amongst (Co-)Chairs. The dates (as of the Helsinki meeting) for subsequent (Co-)Chairs Forums read as follows:

- **November 15, 2024** (*not held by petition of the (Co-)Chairs during the Helsinki meeting*).
- **May 15, 2025**
- **November 13- 14, 2025** (*As 15 is on a weekend, dates in discussion*) – *To be hosted by the University of Graz.*
- **May 15, 2026** –
- **November 15, 2026** – TBC by local organiser.

Four (Co-)Chairs Forums are yet to be held.

6. Conclusion

This document compiles the contributions of all WGs to CoARA, as well as to the broader reform of research assessment, covering progress up to Month 18. It demonstrates that the WGs have been committed to achieving their objectives and highlights key accomplishments. Additionally, the report includes conclusions and main takeaways from the two (Co-)Chairs Forums held to date.

Upcoming tasks include providing continued operational support to both the current and future cohorts of WGs, fully implementing the monitoring plan, and organising the remaining four (Co-)Chairs Forums. A final progress report (D4.4) will be prepared by MCAA at the conclusion of the project (Month 36).

At the conclusion of CoARA Boost, all activities conducted by the Working Groups will be consolidated into a comprehensive document, reflecting the valuable contributions made by volunteers who have dedicated their efforts in-kind towards a shared goal – the reform of research assessment. This compilation will acknowledge their commitment and serve as a lasting record of collective progress towards meaningful change.

7. Annex 1: (Co)-Chairs KOM meeting agenda and minutes.

CoARA Boost WP4 Support to CoARA WGs

First CoARA WGs (Co-)Chairs Meeting

17 November 2023 | 10:30 – 12:00 (CEST)

Details to connect:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/85327443104?pwd=OAAxfZgMHjs0Q4zkqzbNKHNTbf7hfS.1>

Meeting ID: 853 2744 3104

Passcode: 458769

Draft agenda:

10:30 – 10:35	Welcome to participants <i>MCAA and YERUN will welcome participants to the first (Co-)Chairs meeting.</i>
10:35 – 10:55	Introduction of the participants and each WG <i>Round of (Co-)Chairs introduction (by one representative per WG) and brief WG contextualization -topic and work ahead, two minutes per WG.</i>
10:55 – 11:15	WP4 Introduction and Operational Framework <i>Introduction of WP4 ('Support to CoARA WGs') partners and presentation of the Operational Framework – the framework defining the support package to CoARA WGs.</i>
11:15 – 11:25	Coordination with the CoARA Secretariat and Communication <i>Presentation by ESF on the support to WGs regarding communication.</i>
11:25 – 11:55	Discussion <i>Participants will engage on a discussion regarding the support of CoARA Boost towards WGs.</i>
11:55 – 12:00	Wrap-up and next steps <i>MCAA and YERUN will wrap-up the session and outline the next steps.</i>

COARA Boost – (Co-)Chairs Forum (Minutes)

17.11.2023. KOM Meeting (10:30 – 12:00 CET)

List of participants (alphabetical order per WG):

Affiliation	Co-chair representative	WG
Eurodoc	Sebastian Dahle	Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture
Luxembourg National Research Fund	Sean Sapcariu	Experiments in Assessment – Idea generation, co-creation, and piloting
KK-stiftelsen	Yvonne Fors	Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals
European Commission	Jean-Emmanuel Faure	Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals
European Commission	Javier L. Albacete	Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals
DFG	Anna Christa	Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals
DFG	Matthias Kiesselbach	Improving practices in the assessment of research proposals
Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	Janne Pölonen	Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment
Initiative for Science in Europe	Monica Dietl	Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment
MCAA	Gian Maria Greco	Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment
Formas	Josefin Wangel	<i>Please include WG</i>
cOAlition S - ESF	Nora Papp	Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review
cOAlition S	Johan Rooryck	Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review
EUA	Rita Morais	Reforming Academic Career Assessment
EUA	Vinciane Gaillard	Reforming Academic Career Assessment
EU-LIFE	Iris Uribesalgo	Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance
Poznan University of Economics and Business	Katarzyna Nawrot	Responsible metrics and indicators
CRAC-VITAE	Emma Day	Support to WGs
European Science Foundation	Erzsebet Toth-Czifra	Support to WGs
Science Europe	James Morris	Support to WGs
ALLEA	Mathijs Vleugel	Support to WGs

MCAA (WP lead)	Mostafa Moonir Shawrav	Support to WGs
YERUN (WP lead)	Raquel Vega Rubio	Support to WGs
YERUN (WP lead)	Sanja Terlevic	Support to WGs
YERUN (WP lead)	Silvia Gomez Recio	Support to WGs
Charité Universitaetsmedizi n Berlin	Miriam Kip	Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance
OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola	Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
Leiden University	Clifford Tatum	Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
OpenAIRE	Giulia Malaguarnera	Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
Zurich University of Applied Sciences	Martin Jaekel	Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts
Hochschullehrerbun d Bundesvereinigung	Thomas Brunotte	Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts
Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	Claudia Labisch	Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts???
Leibniz Association	Raimund Bleischwitz	Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts

Purpose of the meeting

MCAA and YERUN kicked off the (Co-)Chairs Forum in order to get to know the (Co-)Chairs of the 10 established WGs and discuss the parameters of WP4's support package, included in the Operational Framework (OF). The draft outline of the document was presented to the group and discussed.

Materials used for the meeting (link):

- [WP4 Partners presentation on the OF.](#)
- [ESF's presentation on the communication tools and processes.](#)

Key discussion points

After the introduction of the (Co-)Chairs representatives and the supporting partners of CoARA Boost WP4 (namely, MCAA, YERUN, ALLEA, CRAC-VITAE and SE), the presentation of the Operational Framework followed. The main elements were (see presentation for greater detail):

- Main aim of the OF: To define and delineate the support package to CoARA's Working Groups (WGs) and the mechanisms for communication processes, including internal and external.
- The OF is divided in:
 1. Definitions of the roles of the actors involved
 2. Support Package to WGs (so-called Operational Support Perimeter). **Once the WGs are distributed to WP4 partners, each WP4 partner may discuss with the (Co-)Chairs to decide what specific support is required and most relevant to the group.**
 - High-level support
 - Operational Support
 - Communication (included in ESF's -WP7- presentation)
 3. Monitoring approach, including a template to monitor progress
 4. Quality assurance and oversight procedures
 5. Risk management analysis

6. Environment and sustainability considerations
 7. Ethical and social responsibility guidelines
- Discussions on the draft outlined involved concluded on the next points:
 - **Endorsement process:** WG (Co-)Chairs mentioned that they missed more clarification about the endorsement process of the deliverables of WGs and publication policy. The CoARA [Rules of Procedure](#) document for WGs (p. 7) establishes that the Steering Board will define the mechanisms for the WGs' output endorsement process and publication policy. This endorsement process should consider when a deliverable of the WGs can be open for consultation to the wider CoARA community. The process should avoid a potential review fatigue from the CoARA community and ensure that the WG outputs presented for review are essential outputs of the WGs. This doesn't prevent the notion that every WG's work is valued equally in the CoARA community and that all WG will share important outputs with the CoARA community. There won't be a hierarchy of importance among WGs but within WG outputs, as appropriate. WGs. Once the process is decided by the SB, it can be included in the WP4 Operational Framework.
 - **Meetings of the (Co-)Chairs Forum** will take place biannually but WP4 supporting partners (or "*liason contacts*") will make sure to gather all the relevant information in order to have targeted meetings with the (Co-)Chairs of the groups they support and among themselves.
 - **The monitoring plan and template:** (Co-)Chairs mentioned that a template for monitoring purposes would be useful only if very simple and to facilitate the work the (Co-)Chairs have to do in their reporting to the Steering Board.
 - **Data management guidelines** to be included in section 7 (monitor implementation of CoARA's Code of Conduct).
 - **The allocation of WGs** to supporting partners (WP4) will be a priority so the WGs have a contact point as soon as possible.

The meeting continued with the presentation of the communication processes and tools by ESF (WP7 of CoARA Boost, see presentation for greater detail):

- It was decided that a SharePoint and Teams space will be set up for WG chairs alongside a Zenodo community dedicated to CoARA WGs where they can share their outputs, slides etc. This will be mirrored to the CoARA website.
 - Both the **Teams and the Zenodo** hub will be set up in the coming days. After testing, ESF will inform accordingly when the platforms are ready and running smoothly.
- A membership-level unified exchange point, like Slack or Discord, is not needed at this point.
 - By M7 of the CoARA Boost project (started in October 2023), a **new membership management platform** will be implemented for the entire CoARA coalition. It will keep track of WGs' member data alongside the general CoARA membership, both on institutional and individual contributor levels. Once it's operational, WG Chairs will receive more information about it and access specifications. Currently, the solutions are being landscaped, the membership management platform CVCRM seems to be the most suitable for CoARA.
- It was requested to cover the current long mailing list address (CoARA_WG_(Co-)Chairs Support@esf.org) under a more generic email address dedicated to each CoARA WG.
 - The **CoARA website** is in the progress of changing its domain. This also implies a change in the email address (from the *coara.eu* email to *coara.org*). The change will be in place in a month's time. It is advisable to wait until the domain is changed to create the email addresses.

Next steps

- The allocation of WGs to supporting partners (WP4) will be made in the next weeks (MCAA/YERUN).

- Supporting WP4 partners to communicate and set dates for the (Co-)Chairs Forum (MCAA/YERUN).
- The Teams and the Zenodo hub will be set up in the coming days (ESF).

The email address change will be made in a month time (ESF).